

ESTABLISHMENT OF A DUAL SYSTEM OF TEACHING IN
PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION OF UZBEKISTAN.

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Abstract: *by the Cabinet of Ministers dated 29.03.2021*

*“Organization of dual education in the vocational education system
on measures*

Resolution No. 163 was adopted.

Glossary: *normative, dual education, professional, competence*

The draft resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the establishment of a dual system of training in vocational education of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was discussed on the portal of discussion of normative legal acts.

The document approves the Regulation on the procedure for organizing a dual system of training in vocational education of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

It should be noted that the theoretical, educational and practical part of the dual education program in a professional educational institution, the practical part related to the production of skills and competencies in the enterprise (organization).

According to the project, dual education will be established by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the proposal of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional and Tashkent city khokimiyats, ministries and departments.

According to the document, Dual education graduates can pursue future employment at their own discretion. In this case, the company (organization) is not obliged to hire graduates.

In accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", as well as in order to create opportunities to support the interest of young people in the acquisition of professions and specialties, dual education will be organized in the vocational education system from 2021/2022.

The document approved the Regulation on the organization of dual education in the system of vocational education, which provides for the following:

- organization and stages of dual education;
- the order of the educational process and internships in dual education;
- Defining the duties, rights and responsibilities of dual education participants.

The Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional and Tashkent city khokimiyats, interested ministries and departments have been assigned the following tasks:

- By March 1, regularly study the need for mid-level staff in the relevant professions and specialties in the economy, to establish a system of dual education and identify appropriate measures to ensure the employment of graduates;

- Submit proposals to the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education on organizations where dual education will be organized by April 1.

The Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, as well as agencies with a system of vocational education, have been instructed to:

- Ensuring that students participate in the learning process in vocational education institutions at least two days a week and spend the rest of the working day with practical training in relevant organizations;

- Systematic control over the organization of the dual education process in vocational education institutions;

- Organize a systematic study of international best practices in improving dual education and strengthening methodological support.

Educational institutions enter into contracts with organizations that need staff. There is also a contract between the organization and the students, which provides the student with a specific job.

The tasks of the organization of dual education are:

- Linking the educational process of educational institutions with the production conditions in the enterprise (organization);

- Organize the practical part of education related to production in enterprises (organizations) and the theoretical and practical part of education in educational institutions by turning students into participants in labor activities;

- increase the investment attractiveness of the regions and improve the training of mid-level personnel, taking into account the real needs of the economy;

- Development of formats and models of cooperation between enterprises (organizations) and educational institutions;

- Competence building through the implementation of training programs in conjunction with work activities;

- Improving training programs based on the requirements of employers and their technological innovations;

- funding for training and education programs;

- Improving the forms and methods of sectoral cooperation between enterprises (organizations) and educational institutions;

- further expansion of the participation of enterprises (organizations) in the assessment of graduates;

- Meet the needs of people of different ages to acquire skills in relevant professions (specialties).

Implementing dual education involves the following key steps:

- Identification of enterprises (organizations) for dual education on the basis of proposals of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional and Tashkent city khokimiyats, ministries and departments;

- Concluding a contract between the enterprise (organization) and the educational institution and the enterprise (organization) and the student;
- Identify the need for mid-level staff;
- Career guidance;
- Development and updating of educational programs;
- Organize a dual training process, taking into account the demand and supply of personnel in the labor market;
- Evaluation of personnel trained on the basis of dual education programs.

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